

suggested a modification in the D*/D scheme as

but still could not discriminate between the D*/D and D*/S primary steps.

The yield of ROH in the photolysis of D in anaerobic neutral solutions cannot be satisfactorily explained by the above schemes. Moreover, the formation of only β -ROH in alkaline medium and both α - and β -ROH in neutral and acid medium still remained unexplained. In the D*/S scheme, the formation of DOH⁻ as an adduct of OH⁻ and D in α -position and in β -position is unlikely. Assuming that the adduct is formed, it is yet difficult to justify the DOH⁻ reacting with D to yield DOH⁻ and D⁻ in aerobic medium instead of DOH⁻ directly reacting with oxygen which would mean no production of D⁻. There is, however, positive evidence of formation of D⁻ on photolysis of D in aerobic medium.

Further, the D*/S scheme can not explain (i) the formation of hydroxy-benzoic acid when aqueous solution of D was irradiated in presence of benzoic acid and (ii) the formation of polyhydroxy derivatives of D on prolonged irradiation, though mono-hydroxy derivative has been reported⁵ to be photoinactive.

The present work has been carried out with a view to establish the actual mechanism of the above photochemical reaction.

Experimental

Anthraquinone-2-Na-sulfonate (B.D.H.) was recrystallised five times from water in the dark and dried in a vacuum desiccator over fused CaCl₂. The purity of the compound was estimated by ion exchange process — an aqueous solution of the compound was passed through a cation-exchange resin (IRC-120 in H-form) column and the exchanged anthraquinone-2-sulfonic acid was estimated by titrating with a standard alkali solution.

The light source used was a medium pressure mercury vapour lamp (of M/S. Thermal Syndicate, U.K., model no. T/MS/577, 80 watts), mounted vertically on an optical bench. For isolating 366 nm radiation, the light after collimation was passed through a Chance's -O-O-glass filter and CuSO₄ solution [250 g/litre in 0.01 N H₂SO₄] of 1 cm path length. The irradiation cell (capacity 3 ml; path length 1 cm) was maintained at a constant temp of 29 ± 0.1°. Light output was measured by ferrioxalate actinometry according to a modified method of Hatchard and Parker¹¹.

Aerobic photolysis :

Hydroxy-derivatives of anthraquinone-2-sulfonate were estimated according to the method of Clark and Stonehill⁶. For neutral and acidic solution the absorption at 476 and 491 nm were noted

after alkalination to pH > 11. The extinction coefficients for α - and β -hydroxy derivatives at the above two wavelength are, $\epsilon_{476}^{\beta} = 3.6 \times 10^4$ lit. mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹, $\epsilon_{491}^{\beta} = 3.4 \times 10^4$ lit. mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹, $\epsilon_{476}^{\alpha} = 5.09 \times 10^4$ lit. mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and $\epsilon_{491}^{\alpha} = 5.65 \times 10^4$ lit. mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹, as reported by Clark and Stonehill⁶. For alkaline solution, it was assumed that only β -derivative was being formed and was estimated from the absorption of the photolysed solution at 476 nm. H₂O₂, produced on aerobic irradiation, was estimated by the method of Allen *et al*¹². 1 ml of the photolysed solution was mixed with 1 ml of the reagent (a), [a solution of 1 g NaOH, 33 g KI and 0.1 g (NH₄)₂Mo₇O₂₄·4H₂O in 500 ml water] and 1 ml of reagent (b), (10 g potassium hydrogen phthalate in 500 ml water). H₂O₂ was estimated from the absorption of the solution at 350 nm, after correcting for the absorptions of anthraquinone-sulfonate and its hydroxy derivatives at that wavelength.

Anaerobic photolysis :

The solutions were deoxygenated by bubbling high purity Argon (IOL AR 2 grade of Indian Oxygen Ltd.) through the solution for 1 hr before irradiation.

Irradiation under anaerobic condition of aqueous solution of anthraquinone-2-sulfonate in acidic or neutral medium produced an absorption maximum at 385 nm which disappeared on oxygenation. Similar irradiation in alkaline medium showed absorption maxima at 400 and 500 nm which disappeared on oxygenation leaving a broad band at 476 nm. The spectra of the photolysed solution under anaerobic medium and that after subsequent aeration were recorded with a Beckmann DU spectrophotometer. The difference of the two gave the spectra of the reduced species.

In order to identify the reduced product, D has been reduced with sodium dithionite under anaerobic medium both in acid and alkaline medium. A closed cell containing weighed amount of solid dithionite was thoroughly deoxygenated with high purity argon and then 3 ml of a solution of D (also deoxygenated) was added to it with a syringe. To produce semiquinone (DH[•]) and semiquinolate (D^{•-}), ion the amount of dithionite taken was such that less than 50% reduction occurred. The spectra of quinol (DH₂) and quinolate (D⁻²) ion produced by adding excess of dithionite were also recorded. Hydroxy derivatives produced on anaerobic irradiation were estimated from the oxygenated solution by the method used in the case of aerobic irradiation.

Determination of extinction coefficient of DH[•] : Though earlier workers¹³ reported the extinction coefficient of DH[•], they determined this value from the transient spectra recorded 20 μ sec after pulse radiolysis of Ar-saturated solution of D at pH 4 (after subtraction of DOH and D⁻ contribution) assuming that the ionisation equilibrium (DH[•] $\rightleftharpoons$ D^{•-} + H⁺) is established very soon after the pulse. But it has been found from flash photolysis studies¹⁴ that this ionisation equilibrium is attained not

before a few milliseconds which means that the determination may suffer from non-attainment of equilibrium, leading to an incorrect extinction coefficient.

In the present determination, the species $DH^{\cdot}$ was produced by reducing Ar-saturated solution of D with dithionite in acid medium by the method mentioned earlier and its spectrum was recorded. The solution was then made alkaline by adding 0.3 ml alkali (previously deoxygenated), with the help of a syringe when $DH^{\cdot}$ was converted to $D^{\cdot-}$ and the spectrum was recorded again. Using the extinction co-efficient of $D^{\cdot-}$ at 500 nm, previously determined by electrochemical reduction of D, the concentration of semiquinone has been determined and the extinction co-efficient of $DH^{\cdot}$ at 385 nm was calculated (taking into consideration the absorption of D at 385 nm). The value is 5.55×10^3 lit. $\text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$, while the previously reported value is 1.2×10^4 , apparently from the use of a lower value for the concentration of $DH^{\cdot}$.

Photolysis of anthraquinone-2-sulfonate in presence of formate and azide in anaerobic medium: Argon-saturated solutions of D ($5 \times 10^{-4} M$) in water, containing various concentrations of sodium formate were irradiated and subsequently analysed for semiquinone and hydroxylated products. The results are tabulated in Table 3. Argon-saturated solution of D ($5 \times 10^{-4} M$) in presence of formate ($1 \times 10^{-1} M$) at different pH were also irradiated (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Variation of quantum yield of semiquinone with pH in presence of formate. $[D] = 5 \times 10^{-4} M$; $[\text{formate}] = 1 \times 10^{-1} M$

Argon-saturated solutions of D ($5 \times 10^{-4} M$) in water containing various concentration of azide were irradiated. The results are tabulated in Table 4.

Results and Discussion

Only mono-hydroxylated anthraquinone-2-sulfonate and hydrogen peroxide were identified as stable product after photolysis under aerobic condition.

In acid and neutral medium both α - and β -hydroxy derivatives were formed, the ratio being 3:2 independent of irradiation time. In alkaline medium (at $pH > 10$) only β -hydroxy derivative was detected.

The quantum yields of hydroxy derivatives are matched by an equal yield of H_2O_2 (Table 1) and increases with (i) increase in initial concentration of D (Table 2) and (ii) decrease in irradiation time (Table 1). The dependence of quantum yield on initial concentration of D suggests the involvement of ground state quinone in the overall reaction. The yield is independent of pH in the range 2.5-10, but rises sharply for $pH > 10$.

TABLE 1(a)—IRRADIATION IN NEUTRAL MEDIUM
 $[D] = 5 \times 10^{-4} M$

Time of irradiation in sec.	Aerobic medium		Anaerobic medium	
	ϕ_{ROH}	$\phi_{H_2O_2}$	ϕ_{ROH}	$\phi_{DH^{\cdot}}$
600	1.52×10^{-3}	1.42×10^{-3}		
900	1.49×10^{-3}	1.39×10^{-3}		
1200	1.47×10^{-3}	1.39×10^{-3}	2.74×10^{-3}	4.52×10^{-3}
1500	1.46×10^{-3}	1.37×10^{-3}	2.71×10^{-3}	4.49×10^{-3}

TABLE 1(b)—IRRADIATION IN ALKALINE MEDIUM
 $[\text{OH}^-] = 0.01 N$; $[D] = 5 \times 10^{-4} M$

Time of irradiation in sec.	Aerobic medium		Anaerobic medium	
	ϕ_{ROH}	$\phi_{H_2O_2}$	ϕ_{ROH}	$\phi_{D^{\cdot-}}$
600	4.23×10^{-3}	3.97×10^{-3}	2.02×10^{-3}	3.96×10^{-3}
900	3.90×10^{-3}	3.58×10^{-3}	1.73×10^{-3}	3.34×10^{-3}
1200	3.58×10^{-3}	3.27×10^{-3}	1.64×10^{-3}	3.23×10^{-3}
1500	3.30×10^{-3}	3.02×10^{-3}	1.50×10^{-3}	3.05×10^{-3}

Irradiation under anaerobic medium produces mono-hydroxy derivatives together with semiquinone/semiquinolate ion, thus suggesting the involvement of solvent molecule in the hydroxylation of D. No hydrogen peroxide could be detected when the estimation is carried out under anaerobic medium. With change of pH, similar distribution of isomeric hydroxy derivatives as with aerobic irradiation is observed. The quantum yield of semiquinone/semiquinolate ion is almost twice that of hydroxy derivatives and increases with (i) increase in initial concentration of D (Table 2) and (ii) decrease in irradiation time (Table 1).

For a fixed initial concentration of the quinone in alkaline medium the quantum yield of hydroxy derivative under anaerobic condition is slightly less than half of that under aerobic condition, while in acid and neutral medium the anaerobic yield is about one sixth of the aerobic yield. Results of Table 3 show that on irradiation of D in presence of formate (a known $\text{OH}^{\cdot}$ radical scavenger) the yield of hydroxy derivatives decreases, while that of semiquinone/semiquinolate ion increases compared to that in absence of formate. With increase in formate concentration, the yield of hydroxylated product decreases (and above $10^{-3} M$ formate, no hydroxy product can be detected) with concurrent increase of semiquinone yield. If the formate had acted only

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF QUANTUM YIELDS WITH [D]

Concentration of D in moles/litre	Neutral medium		Alkaline medium; OH ⁻ = 0.1 N		
	ϕ_{ROH}	$\frac{\alpha\text{-ROH}}{\beta\text{-ROH}}$	Aerobic medium ϕ_{ROH}	Anaerobic medium ϕ_{ROH}	$\phi_{D^{\cdot-}}$
5×10^{-3}	4.84×10^{-2}	1.52		8.57×10^{-2}	1.69×10^{-1}
4×10^{-3}	4.57×10^{-2}	1.58	1.75×10^{-1}	7.81×10^{-2}	1.53×10^{-1}
3×10^{-3}	4.21×10^{-2}	1.54	1.58×10^{-1}	6.95×10^{-2}	1.38×10^{-1}
2×10^{-3}	3.63×10^{-2}	1.43	1.43×10^{-1}	4.67×10^{-2}	9.26×10^{-2}
1×10^{-3}	2.54×10^{-2}	1.44	9.41×10^{-2}	2.92×10^{-2}	5.76×10^{-2}
5×10^{-4}	1.51×10^{-2}	1.62	5.90×10^{-2}		

TABLE 3—VARIATION OF QUANTUM YIELD OF SEMIQUINOLATE ION (D^{•-}) AND HYDROXY DERIVATIVE OF D (ROH), ON PHOTOLYSIS OF ANTHRAQUINONE-2-SULFONATE SOLUTION ($5 \times 10^{-4} M$) AT pH = 11.2 WITH DIFFERENT CONCENTRATION OF NA-FORMATE (UNDER ANAEROBIC CONDITION)

Initial concentration of Na-formate in moles/litre	No. of light quanta absorbed per second	No. of molecules of ROH formed per second	No. of molecules of D ^{•-} formed per second	Quantum yield of ROH ϕ_{ROH}	Quantum yield of D ^{•-} $\phi_{D^{\cdot-}}$
8.0×10^{-1}	3.383×10^{15}	—*	1.948×10^{15}	—*	5.76×10^{-1}
4.0×10^{-1}	3.411×10^{15}	—	1.727×10^{15}	—	5.06×10^{-1}
1.0×10^{-1}	3.466×10^{15}	—	1.461×10^{15}	—	4.22×10^{-1}
5.0×10^{-2}	3.496×10^{15}	—	1.218×10^{15}	—	3.49×10^{-1}
2.0×10^{-2}	3.549×10^{15}	—	9.516×10^{14}	—	2.68×10^{-1}
1.0×10^{-2}	3.577×10^{15}	—	7.860×10^{14}	—	2.20×10^{-1}
5.0×10^{-3}	3.605×10^{15}	4.183×10^{13}	5.979×10^{14}	1.16×10^{-2}	1.66×10^{-1}
2.5×10^{-3}	3.605×10^{15}	6.074×10^{13}	4.650×10^{14}	1.68×10^{-2}	1.29×10^{-1}

*—' indicates conc. below limit of detection.

as a scavenger of OH[•] radical (a possible precursor of ROH yield) as suggested by Clark and Stonehill, the decrease of ROH yield in its presence would not have resulted in a concurrent increase of semiquinone yield. The lower yield of ROH may be due to higher reactivity of formate than water towards the intermediate which reacts with water producing ROH. This is further supported by the results in Fig. 1. The pK value of formic acid is 3.75. The results indicate that at and above pH 4.75, where it exists as HCOO⁻, the quantum yield of semiquinone is appreciably higher compared to that below pH 3 where it exists exclusively in the undissociated HCOOH form, and in between pH 3 - 4.75 the yields increase with increase in pH due to increase of the ratio HCOO⁻/HCOOH in the solution.

The variation of the yield of semiquinone with pH in presence of formate can be correlated with the observed dependence of ROH yield on pH in absence of any added substrate. In the pH range 2.5 - 10, where OH⁻ ion concentration is much less than that of quinone usually used ($10^{-3} M$), the yield is much lower because of the fact that undissociated H₂O participates in the reaction and hence pH has no effect on the yield of ROH in this region. Above pH 10, the yield of ROH and semiquinone increases with increase in pH, due to the reason that at OH⁻ concentration higher than $10^{-4} M$, this ion participates in the reaction and the yield increases due to its higher reactivity than H₂O.

Table 4 shows the variation of ROH and semiquinone yield with added NaN₃. In presence of NaN₃ both the ROH and semiquinone yield decreases and at higher concentration of azide no semiquinone as well as ROH formation is observed.

This suggests that azide probably scavenges a common precursor of both ROH and semiquinone.

TABLE 4—QUANTUM YIELD OF ROH AND SEMIQUINONE ON IRRADIATION OF ANTHRAQUINONE-2-SULFONATE ($5 \times 10^{-4} M$) SOLUTION IN PRESENCE OF NaN₃ AT pH 11.2

Concentration of NaN ₃	Quantum yield of ROH	Quantum yield of D ^{•-}
$5 \times 10^{-3} M$	1.62×10^{-2}	3.08×10^{-2}
$1 \times 10^{-2} M$	6.67×10^{-3}	1.31×10^{-2}
$1 \times 10^{-1} M$	0	0

The D[•]/S scheme, in addition to its draw-backs as discussed earlier, can not explain the higher reactivity of OH⁻ and HCOO⁻ compared to H₂O and HCOOH and thus the possibility of its involvement is excluded. The D[•]/D scheme, after modification by Clark and Stonehill, can explain the observed results qualitatively, but it fails to explain the observed variations of ROH yield and α -ROH/ β -ROH ratio with pH. To account for these observations we suggest that D^{•+} must be reacting with OH⁻ at pH > 10 and at pH below 10, it reacts with H₂O molecule. The D[•]/D scheme with modified steps (4) and (5) is given below :

Fig. 2. Dependence of photohydroxylation yield on concentration of 'D': (a) neutral medium (aerobic), (b) alkaline medium (anaerobic), (c) alkaline medium (aerobic).

Indeed this can well explain the observed decrease in the rate of oxidation of alcohol in alkaline medium due to higher reactivity of OH⁻ than H₂O towards D⁺.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the C.S.I.R., New Delhi for financial assistance.

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